

Tool: Calendar Canvas

Description	The tool is simply an A0 printed calendar of the pilot and allows to collectively decide on the actual schedule of activities and tasks during the pilot, and to formalize the actual commitment of participants.
Why am I doing it?	To develop a detailed plan of actions across the remaining phases of the project (data collection, analysis, dissemination, and legacy) and assign people to specific tasks.
Resources needed	public space; A0 printed Calendar Canvas; one facilitator; pens, post-its and pins.
Time needed	1 - 3 hours depending on the number of participants
Skills needed (Not Required, Basic, Intermediate, Advanced)	Subject-matter expertise: Basic IT skills: Not Required Facilitation skills: Intermediate Event organization skills: Intermediate Project management skills: Intermediate Communication skills: Intermediate
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The extended team convenes in a public space in a workshop format. 2. Depending on the agreed data collection instruments (if any beyond Telraam), a set of action points are co-defined and mapped onto the calendar. 3. Hence, participants assign their names to the actions they are most interested in and competent about. 4. Specific tasks for each individual are outlined as a result of this step.
Outcomes	Established pilot schedule, and refined pilot governance framework. Engagement with each participant is formalized across the remaining phases of the pilot.